

ACT
Policy making
Future funding
Participants to evaluate their experience
Does research inform CARE?
Determine what has happened as a result of dissemination
Impact and Grimpact
Learning how to do things better next time
Ethically share
Improved feedback
Policy change
Town hall?
Feedback
Critiques and testimonies
Campaigns for change policy
Create more interest for further research

PARTNER
Social media
New outreach areas (libraries, community leaders, etc.)
Experience team approach: involve public in outreach
Finding funds from public sector
Finding partners for the next phase to design the project
Enhance diversity of voices
Community members could help
Identify involvement groups

DESIGN
Patient involvement
Ensuring inclusivity during the project
Understanding what public/patient consent to
Making sure the study is relevant
Go to public communities, explain in lay terms and accessible images
Understand public views on proposed design and question other ways to improve methods and ensuring that the right questions are asked and why
Public contribution: their thoughts and priorities
Create vested interest early will help on dissemination
Early involvement for inclusivity
"Speed-dating" for science-public relationships
Understand what part of a condition to focus on
Non-patient equivalent
Designing research questions
Informing public
Assessing grant applications
Patient advocacy
Understand what needs to be explained
Gather lived experience
Co-design is crucial

IMPERIAL

COLLECT
Patient involvement in collecting data
Transparency is important for the public to know
What/why/when/who has access (e.g., insurance companies, GDPR)
Safety for public
Communicating what needs to be done and why
Go to the public and consider their needs individually
Making public comfortable to say no and withdraw
Community leader involvement for trust
Advertising effectively and via relevant routes
Reaching out the right communities (demographics, socio-economics, ethnicity...)
Providing training to gather data (qualitative and quantitative)
Designing questionnaire
Bringing those communities to lab to understand the context
Kingston "Lab in a lorry"
Data collection from as diverse parts of population as possible

DISSEMINATE
Create opportunities to share findings in the community
Ensuring participants receive results of research
Ensuring results are in clear language for non-experts
Taking advices from participants where to disseminate findings
Lay language
'Question time' for science
Open access: different media/routes that public use; reach out to relevant, specific varied audiences
Get advice for how to share sensitive data and what can be ethically shared
Barriers to sharing that may be unethical
Recognition for those involved
Short, informative content explaining research
"Space-style"
Create forums like this workshop
Engaging with public before publication
Talking with other people (participants, public, patients)

Public involvement in different stages of the research lifecycle

ANALYSE
Having good reliable info from patients will help to understand data
Members of public in Data Monitoring Committees
Determine appropriate ways to group data
Preventing bias (parity in terms of collection and analysis)
Transparency: outreach activities to try data analysis
Open data with easy interpretation explanation (we have this for global health)
Exploring the ways that public can be involved in analysis

**Beyond Open Research:
Developing a Proof-of-Concept
to Embed Quality and Reliability**